

MODERN TECHNOLOGIES FOR THE DISPOSAL AND RECYCLING OF CARDBOARD PACKAGING

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Abstract

This article examines modern technologies for the disposal and recycling of cardboard packaging (CP), which have become increasingly relevant amidst global consumption growth and rising waste volumes. Both traditional and innovative recycling methods are explored, including mechanical, chemical, and enzymatic treatment, as well as physicochemical approaches such as hydrothermal and plasma processing. The role of digital technologies, including artificial intelligence (AI) and the Internet of Things (IoT), in optimizing sorting processes and carbon footprint monitoring is analyzed. Special attention is given to the environmental aspects and efficiency of modern recycling methods, which help reduce environmental impact and decrease the use of virgin raw materials.

Keywords: cardboard packaging (CP) recycling, chemical treatment, enzymatic recycling, physicochemical methods, digital technologies, carbon footprint, sustainable development.

Introduction

With the global increase in consumption and waste volumes, the issues of recycling and disposal of cardboard packaging (CP) have become particularly relevant. Cardboard materials are widely used across various industries, from the food sector to e-commerce, leading to their significant share in waste structures. Low recycling rates and improper disposal of CP exacerbate environmental issues, such as pollution and increased carbon footprints. In the context of a shift towards more sustainable production and consumption models, addressing CP recycling has become especially critical.

Cardboard, although biodegradable, decomposes slowly in landfills, emitting greenhouse gases, including methane, which intensifies climate impact. Another environmental concern is the growing demand for virgin raw materials for packaging production, contributing to the unsustainable use of forest resources. For these reasons, global attention is increasingly focused on developing and implementing technologies that can

reduce the volume of cardboard waste (CW), lower environmental impact, and decrease the reliance on virgin materials.

The goal of this research is to analyze modern technologies for CP disposal and recycling aimed at minimizing environmental damage and improving the efficiency of material reuse. The methodological basis of the study includes a review of scientific literature, analytical reports, and industry studies, which provides an assessment of both the technical and environmental aspects of various recycling technologies.

Main part. The environmental importance of CP recycling

Over the past decades, cardboard recycling in the United States has reached impressive levels: more than 90% of CW is recycled annually, making cardboard the most recyclable packaging material in the country. For instance, in 2022, approximately 34 million tons of CW were recycled, which is 11,7 million tons more than in 2002 (fig. 1).

Figure 1. Cardboard recycling rate in the United States [1]

Despite the high recycling rate, CW remains a significant environmental issue. As a biodegradable material, cardboard decomposes slowly in landfills when improperly disposed of, emitting methane and other greenhouse gases that exacerbate climate impact. Incinerating CW, in turn, results in CO₂ emissions and other

harmful compounds, contributing to further atmospheric pollution. This highlights the importance of optimizing disposal processes and implementing modern recycling technologies aimed at minimizing environmental damage. The benefits of CP recycling are not

limited to reducing waste and emissions. It also decreases the consumption of virgin raw materials, thus conserving forest resources and supporting the circular economy.

Analysis of traditional CP recycling methods

The recycling process for CP begins with several basic steps, including the collection, sorting, cleaning and actual processing of raw materials. Initially, CW is collected from various sources, such as residential, industrial, and commercial sites. The collected cardboard is then transported to sorting stations, where it is separated into different types and categories for optimal recycling. After sorting, the material undergoes cleaning to remove impurities, including staples, plastic films,

and other non-cellulose elements, improving the quality of the final product. The cleaned CW is sent for processing, where it is shredded, softened with water, and turned into pulp suitable for producing new cardboard and other paper products. This semi-finished product forms the basis for creating finished recycled materials, which can be used to produce new CP and other paper items.

Several traditional recycling methods are employed to convert CW into reusable raw materials effectively. Each method involves specific stages and impacts the material differently, with unique limitations and environmental considerations (table 1).

Table 1.

Traditional methods of cardboard recycling [2, 3]

Recycling method	Description	Limitations
Mechanical processing	Shredding cardboard and turning it into a pulp suitable for creating new products.	Limited possibilities of cleaning from contamination and the need for additional sorting.
Energy processing	Incineration of CW for the production of heat and electricity.	High emissions of CO ₂ and other harmful substances are less preferable from an environmental point of view.
Ink removal (deinking)	Purification of cellulose from inks and dyes by chemical and mechanical influences.	The cost of chemical reagents, the need for additional purification processes.
Manufacture of secondary products	Using recycled cardboard to create new packaging, corrugated cardboard, office paper.	The product quality may be lower than that of products made from primary raw materials, and pre-cleaning is required.

According to the author, traditional methods of CP recycling are essential tools for reducing waste volumes and reusing raw materials. However, each of these methods has its limitations, such as high emissions from incineration, the need for complex cleaning during mechanical recycling and deinking, and the decreased quality of products made from secondary raw materials. These limitations underscore the need to develop and implement new recycling methods that are eco-friendlier and more efficient. To achieve sustainable environmental goals, investments in technologies that can improve purification, enhance the quality of secondary materials, and minimize environmental impact are necessary.

Innovations in CP recycling

Modern CP recycling methods represent significant improvements over traditional approaches, offering more eco-friendly and efficient technologies. These methods enable deeper material processing and reduced environmental impact, making them promising amid increasing waste volumes and stricter environmental regulations.

One innovative method is **chemical recycling of cardboard**, which involves using special reagents to break down cellulose fibers and remove impurities such as ink, glue, and dyes. This process ensures a high level of cleanliness and turns CW into raw materials nearly matching the quality of the original material. Unlike traditional methods, chemical recycling can handle stubborn contaminants, yielding clean, strong, and high-quality secondary fiber suitable for creating premium packaging. The chemical recycling process begins with preparing and shredding waste, followed by

treatment with chemical reagents. Commonly used substances include acids, alkalis, and various solvents that break the intermolecular bonds in cellulose fibers, facilitating the breakdown of cardboard structure and contaminant removal. This dissolving process not only purifies the fibers but also softens them, preparing them for subsequent washing and filtration.

Despite its high effectiveness, chemical recycling requires careful control over reagent use and its environmental impact. One of the main challenges is that some chemicals used can pose ecological risks if not properly disposed of or treated after recycling. To mitigate environmental impact, facilities employing chemical recycling implement reagent purification and regeneration systems, as well as waste processing systems for chemical treatment.

An example of successful implementation of chemical recycling is **Georgia-Pacific**, a leading paper product manufacturer. The company actively uses chemical recycling with special reagents for deep cellulose fiber purification, enabling high-quality secondary raw material production. Results have shown that this method effectively removes complex contaminants, ensuring the cleanliness and strength of the final material comparable to virgin raw materials [4].

One of the most eco-friendly and promising methods of CW recycling is **enzymatic degradation**, which uses microorganisms and enzymes to break down cellulose fibers. This biotechnological approach avoids the use of aggressive chemical reagents, making the process safe for the environment. Enzymatic degradation relies on the ability of specific microorganisms, such as bacteria and fungi, to produce enzymes that

break down cellulose, the primary component of cardboard. The most effective enzymes for this process are cellulases, which break down long cellulose molecule chains into simpler sugars. These sugars can then be converted into valuable products like biomass or used in producing secondary cellulose fibers for the paper industry. Enzymatic degradation occurs at moderate temperatures (typically between 20–50°C), minimizing energy consumption.

Enzymatic recycling is highly environmentally safe, as it requires almost no toxic reagents and produces low emissions. This makes the method suitable for use near populated areas and in sensitive ecosystems. It also ensures a clean final product, as biological processes remove impurities and contaminants from the fibers. This makes enzymatic recycling particularly suitable for creating secondary raw materials fit for producing CP that can contact food and pharmaceuticals. Another significant advantage of enzymatic recycling is its low energy requirement. The moderate temperature process minimizes energy use, reducing operational costs and the carbon footprint of recycling. This makes cardboard recycling biotechnology an attractive option for countries aiming to reduce CO₂ emissions and energy consumption.

Companies engaging in enzymatic recycling also achieve impressive results. **Domtar Corporation**, a major producer of paper and packaging materials, uses enzymatic degradation for CW disposal. This has enabled the company to produce clean and safe secondary raw materials suitable for food packaging [5].

Physicochemical methods of cardboard recycling include innovative approaches such as hydrothermal and plasma treatment, which significantly accelerate the breakdown and cleaning of CW, enabling efficient production of high-quality secondary raw materials. These methods combine physical and chemical actions, making them highly effective for deep fiber decomposition and contaminant removal. However, high energy requirements make them mainly suitable for industrial applications.

Hydrothermal treatment involves using high temperatures (200–300°C) and pressure (10 to 25 atmospheres) to accelerate the breakdown of cellulose fibers. In the presence of water and heat, cellulose and other organic components of cardboard undergo hydrolysis, breaking complex polymers into simpler components such as lignin and simple sugars. This process yields clean cellulose pulp suitable for further recycling. **Plasma treatment** is a physicochemical method that uses high-energy plasma for CW decomposition and cleaning. Plasma, consisting of ionized particles, is generated under high temperatures and electrical voltage and is highly chemically active, capable of breaking down organic contaminants, including persistent chemicals and pigments.

Physicochemical methods of cardboard recycling offer numerous advantages, including high processing speed, effective contaminant removal, and the ability to obtain clean, high-quality secondary raw materials. They also allow recycling of waste containing stubborn impurities, making these methods preferable for processing heavily contaminated cardboard. However, the

main limitations of these methods are high energy costs and equipment complexity.

WestRock uses hydrothermal treatment for deep cellulose fiber breakdown under high temperatures and pressure. This method allows the company to efficiently recycle large volumes of contaminated cardboard, improving secondary raw material quality and reducing recycling time [6].

Modern CP recycling methods provide opportunities for environmentally safe and economically efficient recycling, making them promising for use in the global packaging industry. These innovations address the CW recycling problem in a more sustainable and effective way, contributing to environmental protection and natural resource conservation.

The use of digital technologies in the CP recycling process

Digital technologies play an essential role in improving the efficiency of CP recycling. With the development of artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning, and the Internet of Things (IoT), recycling facilities can optimize production processes, enhance quality control, and reduce their carbon footprint. These technologies increase transparency and adaptability in recycling systems, creating conditions for more sustainable and efficient CW disposal.

At large recycling facilities, **AI** algorithms analyze waste images in real-time, classifying them by type, quality, and contamination level. This automates the sorting process, removing the human factor, which in turn improves accuracy and reduces errors. **Machine learning** is also used to predict the volume and quality of incoming raw materials, helping recycling facilities adapt their processes to changing conditions. For example, algorithms can forecast the expected volume of CW during certain times of the year, allowing for efficient resource planning and lower operational costs [7]. Additionally, AI can identify anomalies in waste composition or characteristics, enabling quick adjustments to production processes and ensuring the quality of the secondary raw materials produced.

Technologies IoT enable the connection and synchronization of different components of the production line, providing control at every stage of CW recycling. Sensors IoT are placed on equipment and conveyor belts to monitor parameters such as incoming waste volume, contamination level, raw material quality, and processing speed. The IoT system collects and analyzes data in real-time, allowing for the prompt detection of process deviations and preventing subpar recycling. For instance, sensors can track contamination levels of raw materials, ensuring that recycled materials meet set quality standards. Also, IoT optimizes the use of resources such as energy and water, reducing the environmental impact and recycling costs. Data integration through IoT enables more accurate forecasting and material planning, which is crucial given fluctuating demand and supply conditions.

In the United States, digital technologies are actively used to monitor the carbon footprint and account for secondary materials within the recycling system. For example, **Waste Management Inc**, one of the largest waste recycling and disposal companies, employs

comprehensive IoT solutions and AI for carbon footprint tracking. Their sensor system allows the company to monitor CO₂ emissions at each recycling stage, while AI algorithms help optimize waste transportation routes, reducing fuel consumption and CO₂ emissions [8].

The digitization of CW recycling through AI, IoT, and other innovations increases system adaptability, allowing for a flexible response to market changes and ecological requirements. These technologies make recycling more precise, efficient, and economically beneficial, aiding in the pursuit of sustainability goals and minimizing environmental impact.

Conclusion

Modern CP recycling technologies offer effective and environmentally responsible solutions for waste disposal and the production of high-quality secondary raw materials. In the context of increasing waste volumes and the global shift toward sustainable production and consumption models, these methods play a critical role in reducing environmental damage and conserving natural resources. Traditional approaches have limitations, prompting the development of innovative methods such as chemical, enzymatic, and physicochemical recycling. These methods enable deeper material processing, the removal of persistent contaminants, and the production of raw materials close in quality to primary ones.

Digital technologies play a particularly important role in optimizing recycling processes and ensuring quality control at all stages. These technologies help companies reduce their carbon footprint, use resources efficiently, and increase overall effectiveness. Thus, the future of CP recycling lies in adopting eco-friendly and energy-efficient technologies that help reduce waste volumes, minimize the use of virgin resources, and lower the environmental impact.

References

1. U.S. cardboard recycling rate 2022 / Statista // URL: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/605383/recovery-rate-of-old-corrugated-containers-in-the-united-states/> (date of application 21.10.2024).
2. Franz R., Welle F. Recycling of post-consumer packaging materials into new food packaging applications – Critical review of the European approach and future perspectives // *Sustainability*. 2022. Vol. 14. №. 2. P. 824.
3. Uliankina I. The Role of Digital Technologies in Climate Change Management: Strategies for Minimizing the Environmental Impact of USA Companies // *Bulletin of Science and Practice*. 2024. Vol. 10. №. 10. P. 62-68.
4. Al-Ameri O. B., Alzuhairi M., Bailon-Garcia E., Carrasco-Marin F., Amaro-Gahete J. Transforming Petrochemical Processes: Cutting-Edge Advances in Kaolin Catalyst Fabrication // *Applied Sciences*. 2024. Vol. 14. – №. 19. P. 9080.
5. Roopchand R., Andrew J., Sithole B. Using a systematic review to develop a cellulose nanocrystals production framework for use as a design baseline and optimization tool // *South African Journal of Chemical Engineering*. 2023. Vol. 44. №. 1. P. 344-355.
6. Jia L., Juneja A., Majumder E. L. W., Ramarao B. V., Kumar D. Efficient enzymatic hydrolysis and polyhydroxybutyrate production from non-recyclable fiber rejects from paper mills by recombinant *Escherichia coli* // *Processes*. 2024. Vol. 12. №. 8. P. 1576.
7. Awogbemi O., Kallon D. V. V., Bello K. A. Resource recycling with the aim of achieving zero-waste manufacturing // *Sustainability*. 2022. Vol. 14. №. 8. P. 4503.
8. Sharma P., Vaid U. Emerging role of artificial intelligence in waste management practices // *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*. – IOP Publishing. 2021. Vol. 889. №. 1. P. 012047.